

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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*Elektron nashr. 675 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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subsequent processing of low-fat milk raw materials and intermediate products [4, 5]. Since whey is a valuable biological raw material that is discarded as production waste, thereby polluting the environment, it would be advisable to use it as the main raw material for preparing food products [6].

The problem of judicious use of whey exists in all countries with a highly developed dairy industry. In countries like France, the USA, Sweden, and Canada, the dairy industry processes 50-95% of dairy waste [7]. Whey processing today is a relevant solution that will reduce the release of pollutants into the environment and increase the level of dairy industry enterprises due to waste-free production [8].

According to the environmental safety aspects of food waste, 1 ton of whey discharged into the sewer pollutes water bodies in the same way as 100 m³ of household waste. Greening dairy production is an integral part of the concept of sustainable development of enterprises developed in recent years. It involves environmentally oriented technical and technological development of the dairy industry, where, as before, there is no clear and complete awareness of the need to green production [6].

The effects of animal proteins in whey are destroyed and create persistent organic pollution of the area when released into the environment. When whey (or water containing it) is discharged into the soil, plant development is inhibited, and with long-term intake of the pollutant, the soil becomes practically infertile. The high acidity of whey leads to the acidification of the soil and the death of its normal microflora. Once in water or soil, the organic substances of whey undergo oxidation, resulting in the formation of a large number of toxic compounds. For these reasons, a more serious and stringent approach to solving the problem of processing secondary raw materials from the dairy industry is required [9].

Whey is considered a valuable secondary raw material, which contains almost all biologically active substances present in milk itself. However, it should not be considered secondary raw material because the content of useful microelements and vitamins in whey is very high. Whey contains components such as lactoferrin, immunoglobulin, a full set of B vitamins, as well as vitamin C, nicotinic acid, choline, vitamin A, vitamin E, and biotin, micro- and macroelements such as Ca, K, P, Fe, Zn, and all essential amino acids [10].

Existing whey disposal technologies (discharge into sewers or filtration fields) lead to serious negative environmental consequences (disruption of sewage treatment plants, mineral salinization of soil, and groundwater). Thus, the need for deep processing of whey and reducing its losses is determined not only by economic feasibility but also by the need to protect the environment [11].

In order to ensure comprehensive processing of dairy raw materials and increase the volume of whey processing, it is advisable to intensify the attraction of investments for modernization and the creation of additional specialized capacities for whey processing. Modern technologies for the processing and use of whey allow considering potential methods such as drying, thickening, ultrafiltration, and the production of protein concentrates, the production of milk sugar and its derivative - lactulose, with subsequent use in the food industry, for feed purposes, and the production of ethyl alcohol [12].

In terms of creating low-waste production, increasing product yield, its nutritional and biological value through the maximum use of all protein components of raw materials, methods of high-temperature coagulation of milk proteins are of interest. The highest degree of utilization of fat and protein substances is achieved by high-temperature coagulation of milk proteins using acids and calcium chloride, called thermoacid and thermocalcium coagulation, respectively. If the efficiency of acid coagulation (without heating) is taken as 100%, the relative degree of use of protein substances during rennet, thermoacid, and thermocalcium coagulation is 94%, 114%, and 116%, respectively [13].

Thus, based on the above review of literature data, the purpose of this research was to study the process of thermal acid coagulation of milk proteins aimed at maximizing the release of whey proteins in combination with casein, which ensures low-waste production and environmental protection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following research methods were used in the work: titratable acidity according to GOST 3624-67; active acidity on the device pH 222; mass fraction of fat according to GOST 5867-69; mass fraction of moisture and dry matter according to GOST 3626-73; content of nitrogenous compounds according to the VNIIMS method. Repeat the analyzes 5 times.

RESULTS

It is known that when milk is heated, whey proteins denature and, when the medium is acidified, they precipitate together with casein. Under conditions of such a decrease in the stability of colloidal milk systems, the properties of the resulting sediment and the completeness of precipitation depend on a number of parameters, among which the main ones can be considered the temperature regime of the coagulation process, the ratio of

coagulant and milk, which determine the charge of colloidal particles and their aggregative stability. In this case, the type and temperature of the coagulant play an important role. To study the results of a preliminary series of experiments, whey with an acidity of 130 - 140 °T was used as a coagulant, obtained by adding pure cultures of lactic acid parts of the rods in an amount of 5%. The coagulation temperature was adjusted to 35 – 40 °C before use.

In order to establish optimal heating temperature ranges, as well as to study the effect of different heating temperatures on physicochemical, organoleptic characteristics, and the degree of utilization of solids, skim milk was heated to the following temperature values: 80, 85, 90, and 95 °C. At the above-mentioned temperatures, pre-prepared acid whey was added into the skim milk in small portions in a thin stream along the wall, carefully placing it. Whey was taken in an amount of 10% of the milk volume. The mixture was left undisturbed for 5 minutes. The isolated proteins were filtered through a Mylar cloth and then self-pressed for 1-2 hours. The total volume of the mixture of skim milk and whey was 1.5 liters. The results of studies of the obtained protein masses and the released whey are given in Table 1.

Table 1. The influence of different heating temperatures on physicochemical, organoleptic characteristics and the degree of utilization of milk solids.

Coagulation temperature, °C	Protein mass				Whey	
	Degree of use of dry substances, %	pH	Taste and smell	Consistency	Mass fraction of protein, %	Mass fraction of dry substances, %
80	22,9	6,00± 0,01	Clean with a slight pasteurization taste	Rough, crumbly	0,520± 0,003	7,00± 0,035
85	39,7	6,01± 0,01	Clean with a slight pasteurization taste	Rough, crumbly	0,443± 0,003	6,55± 0,030
90	43,1	6,00± 0,01	Clean with a taste of pasteurization	Dense, grainy	0,397± 0,004	6,35± 0,037
95	44,7	6,03± 0,01	Clean with a taste of pasteurization	Hard, rubbery	0,359± 0,005	6,18± 0,030

The study of the effect of heat exposure duration on the utilization degree of dry substances in protein masses was conducted at a milk heating temperature of 95°C and an optimal whey addition dose of 10% of the milk volume. Different durations at 95°C were investigated: 10-15 seconds, 5 minutes, 10 minutes, and 20 minutes. The volume of the mixture and the conditions for thermal acid coagulation were the same as in previous experiments, except that, in addition to skim milk, normalized milk with a fat content of 1.1% was also used as the starting raw material. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

In order to study the effect of coagulation temperature on the properties and quality of the resulting protein masses, the starting raw materials (skimmed and normalized milk with a fat content of no more than 1.1%) were subjected to thermal treatment under previously established conditions (95°C with a holding time of 5 minutes) and coagulated with acid whey at temperatures of 95, 85, 75, and 65°C for 5 minutes. After separating the whey and self-pressing for 60 minutes, the resulting protein mass and the released whey were subjected to research.

The study of changes in the physicochemical properties of skim and fat protein masses was conducted by obtaining them at the coagulation temperature of proteins in heat-treated milk at 65, 75, 85, and 95°C (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Analyzing the data obtained at all four studied temperature values, it can be seen that the heating temperature has a significant effect on the degree of utilization of dry substances.

Table 2. The influence of the duration of heat exposure on the degree of utilization of dry substances of protein masses.

No.	Heating temperature, °C	Duration of heat exposure, min	Degree of utilization of dry substances, %		Mass fraction of protein in the released whey, %
			Low-fat protein mass	Fat protein mass	
1	95	0,16-0,25	45,8	45,6	0,364± 0,004
2	95	5	46,1	47,5	0,360± 0,053
3	95	10	46,6	48,3	0,352± 0,003
4	95	20	47,0	48,6	0,350± 0,008

As shown in Table 1, as the heating temperature decreases from 95 to 80°C, the degree of utilization of dry substances decreases from 44.7 to 22.9%. When the heating temperature increases to 95°C, the mass fraction of proteins and dry substances in the released whey decreases by 30.95 and 11.72%, respectively, compared to heating at 80°C.

The increase in the degree of utilization of dry substances in protein masses with increasing heating temperature is associated with denaturation and joint release of whey proteins and casein. Whey proteins are the most sensitive to heat, and therefore their degree of denaturation strongly depends on the heating temperature.

However, the considered heating temperature range does not have a noticeable effect on the active acidity of protein masses and slightly changes their organoleptic characteristics. As the heating temperature decreases, the consistency of the protein masses changes from solid rubbery to grainy crumbly.

As stated above, the degree of utilization of protein solids is closely related to the denaturation of whey proteins. Since the degree of denaturation of whey proteins depends not only on the heating temperature but also on the duration of its exposure, we also studied the effect of this factor. As can be seen from the research results (Table 2), with increasing duration of heat exposure, there is a noticeable increase in the mass fraction of dry substances in protein masses and a decrease in the content of soluble whey proteins in the released whey due to their further denaturation. Thus, increasing the duration of thermal exposure from 10-15 seconds to 5 and 20 minutes increases the degree of utilization of dry substances in skim and fatty protein masses by 0.3, 1.2%, and 1.9, 3.0%, respectively, and reduces the mass fraction of whey proteins in the serum by 0.36 and 2.6%, respectively. However, despite a slight increase in the degree of utilization of dry substances, long-term thermal exposure significantly changes the physicochemical properties of milk and is associated with significant energy costs.

Taking this into account, in further experiments, the duration of thermal exposure did not exceed 5 minutes.

As shown by the study of the duration of exposure of the mixture at the coagulation temperature after adding acid whey, this significantly affects the mass of dry substances in protein masses. When held for 5 minutes, the mass of dry substances in protein masses increases by 20%; a further increase in holding the mixture has virtually no effect on the mass of dry substances in protein masses.

Table 3. Physico-chemical properties of protein masses and whey.

Milk temperature before coagulation, °C	Dose acid whey, %	Mixture temperature, °C	Protein mass				Whey		
			Degree of use of dry substances, %	Mass moisture content, %	pH	Titra-table acidity, °T	Mass fraction of protein, %	Titra-table acidity, °T	pH
Low-fat protein mass									
65	17,3	55	45,4	73,71± 0,21	5,78± 0,01	140,0±1,8	0,362± 0,004	26,9± 0,4	5,73± 0,01
75	15,3	65	46,1	72,42± 0,37	5,92± 0,01	127,0±1,7	0,358± 0,005	22,6± 0,3	5,85± 0,01
85	12,5	75	46,0	71,83± 0,39	6,03± 0,01	113,0±1,5	0,360± 0,019	20,1± 0,3	5,89± 0,01

environmental consequences of the release of whey into the environment and the need for greening dairy production, this technology for processing and using whey, due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness, is recommended for widespread implementation in dairy industry enterprises.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We express our deep gratitude to the management of the Murodzhonsut International Chemistry Association and the staff of the Service department of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service for their assistance in organizing and conducting experimental work.

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Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

